

MULTI-LEVEL FRAMEWORK FOR SCIENTIFIC WRITING

MANUSCRIPT LEVEL

Develop a compelling narrative

Story

Know your story

- Why? – The gap
- What? – The contribution
- So what? – The implications

Abstract

Tell your story in a nutshell

- Background and gap
- Your specific contribution
- Wider significance

Figures and tables

Select display items that convey your story

- Overview
- Results and analysis
- Outlook

Weave figures into the text

Navigability

Guide readers through your story

- Descriptive headings
- Clear leading sentences
- Informative caption titles

SECTION LEVEL

Build a robust overall structure

Title

Describe what you found, not what you did

Limit length, maximize clarity

Include main keywords

Abstract

Provide a self-contained summary tailored to the target readership

Follow the hourglass structure

Keep the 'busy reader' in mind

Introduction

Elaborate on the 'why?', set the scene

Move from the general field to your specific work

Keep the 'general reader' in mind

Methods, results and discussion

Explain the 'what?', substantiate the key claims

Present data and results in a logical sequence

Keep the 'expert reader' in mind

Conclusions

Address the 'so what?', discuss specific implications and limitations

Avoid mere repetition or summary

Keep the 'cross-disciplinary reader' in mind

References

Give credit to others and embed your work in the broader literature

Ensure that each reference is directly relevant and suitably integrated

Check each item for completeness and correct formatting

Supplementary material

Remove barriers to reproducibility

Provide practical resources such as datasets and code

Keep the 'newcomer reader' in mind

PARAGRAPH AND SENTENCE LEVEL

Write coherent, flowing text

Paragraph

Give each paragraph a distinct role and clear internal logic

Employ rigorous signposting, create effective transitions

Use leading sentences that collectively tell the overall story

Sentence

Convey only one message per sentence

Create coherent thematic progression

Ensure parallel structure within sentences

WORD LEVEL

Ensure clarity

Decluttering

- Aim for the minimum complexity possible
- Avoid multi-word constructions
- Remove redundancy

Clarity and precision

Avoid

- Ambiguity
- Excessive passive
- Vague referents

Objectivity and formality

Avoid

- Hype and overconfidence
- Jargon and clichés
- Anthropomorphisms
- Informal style

Checkpoints

Scan for

- Consistent notation
- Em-dashes, en-dashes, hyphens
- Verb tenses